

COMPLEX DICYANOBISETHYLENEDIAMINE COBALTIC COMPOUNDS

BY PRIYADARANJAN RÂY AND BYOMKES SARMA

By the action of potassium cyanide on a solution of *trans*-dithiosulphatobisethylenediamine sodium cobaltiate (Rây and Maulik, this *Journal*, 1933, 10, 655) a univalent cationic new cyano complex, dicyanobisethylenediamine cobaltic thiosulphate was prepared in the form of beautiful silky yellow needles, difficultly soluble in water. Starting from this complex thiosulphate, the complex base and a number of its salts, namely halides, nitrate, sulphate, phosphate, selenate, chromate and molybdate, were obtained. The complex halides were found to form double salts with cupric and mercuric halides. The complex sulphate also gave double sulphates with the sulphates of cobalt, copper and nickel. Argenti- and cuprothiosulphates of the complex base were also prepared.

Conductivity, lowering of the freezing point in aqueous solution, magnetic susceptibility and molecular volumes for some of the complex salts were determined, and the nature of the complex cation discussed.

The same product was obtained also from the *cis*-dithiosulphatobisethylenediamine sodium cobaltiate; hence, the dicyano complex appears to possess a *trans*-configuration.

A new type of cyanocobaltic complex, dicyanobisethylenediamine cobaltic thiosulphate, was prepared by the action of potassium cyanide on a solution of the sodium salt of *trans*-dithiosulphatobisethylenediamine cobaltiate (Rây and Maulik, this *Journal*, 1933, 10, 655). The corresponding sulphate was prepared by oxidising a strong solution of the thiosulphate with silver oxide. From the sulphate, many other salts were obtained by double decomposition with the corresponding barium salts. The hydroxide of the complex base, halides, nitrate, sulphate, biphosphate, selenate, chromate, molybdate, Reineckate, double halides of the complex base with cupric and mercuric halides, double sulphates with copper, cobalt and nickel sulphates, and complex thiosulphates with silver and copper (I) were prepared and their properties studied: Formation of the same yellow compound from both the *cis*- and *trans*-dithiosulphatobisethylenediamine cobaltiate suggests a *trans*-configuration for the complex. Measurement of conductivity of its salts indicates that the complex gives rise to a univalent cation. Like all cobaltic complexes it is found to be diamagnetic.

This new complex forms naturally a member of the family of substituted cyano cobaltic complexes described by Rây and co-workers (Rây, *ibid.*, 1927, 4, 325; *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1932, 208, 392; Rây and Chakrabarty, *ibid.*, 1933, 211, 173; Rây and Gupta Chowdhury, *ibid.*, 1934, 220, 154; Rây and Dutt, *ibid.*, 1937, 234, 65), viz., thiosulphatopentacyano cobaltiate, μ -sulphitodecacyanodicobaltiate, disulphitetetracyano-, diaquotetracyano- and aquopentacyano cobaltiate. But while all these compounds give rise to complex anions, the dicyanobisethylenediamine cobaltic complex, described in this paper, forms the first instance of a complex cyano-cobaltic cation.

The dicyanobisethylenediamine cobaltic complex gives rise to many double salts analogous to those formed by the alkali metals.

In many of its physical properties like molecular conductivity, freezing point of aqueous solution, magnetic susceptibility, etc., it resembles the dichlorodiethylenediamine cobaltic chloride. The equivalent conductivity values at different dilutions, however, seem to suggest that the complex salt suffers slow hydrolysis in aqueous solution at about 30°.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Dicyanobisethylenediamine-cobaltic Thiosulphate.—Sodium dithiosulphatobisethylenediamine cobaltiate (1 mql., 1.7 g.) (Ray and Maulik, *loc. cit.*) was treated with two molecules (0.5 g.) of potassium cyanide with sufficient water on the water-bath. The violet solution turned red. The solution was evaporated to a very small volume, when a pasty solid was obtained. This was filtered on the Buchner, washed first with ice-cold water and then with alcohol. The filtrate was diluted with water and was again evaporated on the water-bath. Another crop of the substance was obtained as before. The process of dilution and subsequent evaporation on the water-bath, was repeated several times to obtain as much of the substance as possible. Finally, all the crops were collected and crystallised from hot water. The substance was dried in air. {Found: Co, 19.86; S, 10.76; N, 28.35; CN, 17.68; H₂O (by loss at 105°), 2.98. [Co(CN)₂(en)₂]₂ S₂O₃·H₂O requires Co, 19.94; S, 10.81; N, 28.38; CN, 17.57; H₂O, 3.04 per cent}.

The substance forms beautiful, silky, long, yellow needles, sparingly soluble in water. It is insoluble in the organic solvents like acetone, alcohol, etc. Specific gravity (d_{4}^{25}) = 1.459.

The substance is very stable, and the complexion is not decomposed by alkalis or acids. Silver nitrate solution produces a greenish precipitate which readily turns black. The substance behaves like alkali thiosulphates and dissolves the precipitate first obtained with silver nitrate or copper sulphate solution.

Equivalent conductivity at 30°.

<i>v</i> (litres.) . . .	32	64	128	256	512	1024
λ^v ..	77.18	92.39	99.84	104.2	113.1	121.2
λ_{∞} ..	94.77	108.30	112.0	113.2	120.0	126.4
					Mean λ_{∞} = 112.45	

The λ_{∞} was calculated from Walden's formula,

$$\lambda_{\infty} = (i + n_1 \times n_2 \times 0.692 v^{-\frac{1}{2}})$$

where *v* is dilution in litres *n*₁ and *n*₂ are the valences of the ions.

Cryoscopic measurements.

Substance (g./50 c.c.) (calculated anhydrous)	Depression (ΔT)	Mol. wt. (<i>m</i>)	Van't Hoff's coeff. (<i>i</i> = <i>M</i> / <i>m</i>)	Degree of dissociation ($\alpha = \frac{i-1}{n-1}$)
0.3673 g.	0.053°	257.8	2.23	0.615

Magnetic Susceptibility.—The magnetic susceptibility of the substance was measured in a Gouy's balance with a field strength of 10.16×10^3 gauss at 30°.

$$\chi_g = -0.2966 \times 10^{-6}; \quad \chi_M = -175.6 \times 10^{-6}$$

The substance lost all its water at 105° and there was no change in colour or composition even at 150°. {Found: Co, 20.67; S, 11.21. [Co(CN)₂(en)₂]₂ S₂O₃ requires Co, 20.56; S, 11.15 per cent}.

When the red coloured *cis*-dithiosulphatobisethylenediamine sodium cobaltate was treated with the calculated amount of potassium cyanide, as described above, the same yellow product was obtained, except that it was anhydrous.

Dicyanobisethylenediamine-cobaltic sulphate was obtained by the oxidation of the complex thiosulphate solution with silver oxide. A strong solution of dicyanobisethylenediamine cobaltic thiosulphate was treated with an excess of freshly prepared silver oxide. After two or three days, the complex sulphate solution was separated from the unacted silver oxide and the resulting silver sulphide by filtration. The filtrate was just acidified with dilute sulphuric acid and concentrated by evaporation on the water-bath. On cooling, voluminous yellow needle-shaped crystals separated out. These were filtered and washed first with ice-cold water and then with absolute alcohol. The substance was purified by recrystallisation from hot water. The substance was dried in air. {Found : Co, 19.50 ; S, 5.24 ; H₂O (by loss at 105°), 8.75. [Co (CN)₂(en)₂]₂ SO₄ · 3 H₂O requires Co, 19.28; S, 5.23; H₂O, 8.82 per cent}.

The substance forms deep yellow crystalline needles. It is sparingly soluble in cold water (2.51 g. in 97.49 g. of water at 30°). It gives double salts with sulphates of copper, nickel and cobalt; but no alum-like product was obtained with aluminium or chromium sulphate.

Specific gravity (d_{4}^{25}) = 1.490.

Dicyanobisethylenediamine-cobaltic Chloride.—Dicyanobisethylenediamine cobaltic sulphate (2.8 g.) in aqueous solution was treated with a solution of barium chloride (1g.). The mixture was heated on the water-bath. The filtrate from barium sulphate contained just a little excess of the complex sulphate. On concentration on the water-bath, the complex sulphate crystallised out first, which was filtered off. On further concentration and subsequent cooling, the dark yellow, large rectangular prisms of the chloride separated from the solution. These were filtered and washed first with ice-cold water and then with absolute alcohol. The product was purified by recrystallisation from hot water, and dried in air. {Found : Co, 22.17 ; Cl, 13.22. [Co(CN)₂(en)₂]Cl requires Co, 22.13 ; Cl, 13.32 per cent}.

The substance is highly soluble in water (13%). It forms double chlorides with those of copper and mercury. Specific gravity (d_{4}^{25}) = 1.371.

Equivalent conductivity at 30°.

v (litres)	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048
λ_v ..	81.47	91.66	97.74	106.6	114.5	117.3	125.1	134.1	139.0
λ_{∞} ..	101.4	107.5	109.6	115.7	121.5	122.4	129.0	137.1	141.0
							Mean λ_{∞} = 120.58		

(Therefore, the mobility of the complex cation = 120.58 — 81.0 = 39.58 ; the mobility of Cl⁻ at 30° = 81).

Cryoscopic measurements.

Sub. (g./50 c.c.) (anhydrous)	Depression (ΔT)	Mol. wt. found. (m)	Van't Hoff's coeff. ($i = M/m$).	Degree of dissociation ($\alpha = \frac{i-1}{n-1}$)
0.4338 g.	0.103°	156.7	1.701	0.701

The result shows that about 70.1% of the substance dissociates at the temperature of the melting point of ice. The complex cation is quite stable and is not decomposed by acids or alkalis.

Dicyanobisethylenediamine-cobaltic bromide was prepared like the complex chloride from a concentrated solution of the complex sulphate and the calculated amount of barium bromide by double decomposition. {Found : Co, 19.01 ; Br, 25.82. $[\text{Co}(\text{CN})_2(\text{en})_2]$ Br requires Co, 18.98 ; Br, 25.70 per cent}. Specific gravity (d_{40}^{25}) = 1.556.

Dicyanobisethylenediamine-cobaltic iodide was prepared from the complex sulphate and barium iodide as in the previous cases. {Found : Co, 16.41 ; I, 35.61. $[\text{Co}(\text{CN})_2(\text{en})_2]$ I requires Co, 16.48 ; I, 35.47 per cent}. Specific gravity (d_{40}^{25}) = 1.708.

Dicyanobisethylenediamine-cobaltic nitrate was prepared from the complex sulphate and barium nitrate. {Found : Co, 20.35 ; NO_3 , 21.15. $[\text{Co}(\text{CN})_2(\text{en})_2]$ NO_3 requires, Co, 20.14 ; NO_3 , 21.15 per cent}. Specific gravity (d_{40}^{25}) = 1.416.

It forms deep yellow fine crystals, readily soluble in water.

Dicyanobisethylenediamine-cobaltic dihydrogen phosphate was obtained from the complex sulphate and barium dihydrogen phosphate. {Found : Co, 17.02 ; P, 8.73 ; H_2O (by loss at 105°), 5.11. $[\text{Co}(\text{CN})_2(\text{en})_2]$ $\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Co, 17.05 ; P, 8.96 ; H_2O , 5.20 per cent}.

Dicyanobisethylenediamine-cobaltic hydroxide was obtained by the action of baryta on an aqueous solution of the complex sulphate. The filtrate from BaSO_4 deposited fine deep yellow crystals on cooling. These were washed and dried as usual. {Found : Co, 23.80 ; OH, (by filtration), 6.80. $[\text{Co}(\text{CN})_2(\text{en})_2]$ OH requires Co, 23.79 ; OH, 6.85 per cent}.

The substance forms a deep yellow micro-crystalline solid. It is extremely soluble in water. The solution of the substance reacts alkaline and liberates ammonia from ammonium salt solution.

Dicyanobisethylenediamine-cobaltic Thiocyanate.—A concentrated solution of the dicyanobisethylenediamine cobaltic sulphate was heated on the water-bath with a strong solution (50%) of ammonium thiocyanate. A beautiful yellow crystalline product was obtained on cooling. The product was washed as usual and dried in air. {Found : Co, 20.26 ; CNS, 20.14. $[\text{Co}(\text{CN})_2(\text{en})_2]$ CNS requires Co, 20.42 ; CNS, 20.07 per cent}.

Dicyanobisethylenediamine-cobaltic Selenate.—A strong solution of dicyanobisethylenediamine-cobaltic hydroxide was neutralised with selenic acid and then a little of the acid in excess was added. The mixture was filtered and evaporated to a small volume on the water-bath. On standing for a few days, beautiful deep yellow needles separated out of the solution. These were washed and dried as usual. {Found : Co, 17.79 ; Se, 12.13 ; H_2O (by loss at 105°), 7.97. $[\text{Co}(\text{CN})_2(\text{en})_2]$ $\text{SeO}_4 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Co, 17.90 ; Se, 12.01 ; H_2O , 8.19 per cent}.

Dicyanobisethylenediamine-cobaltic Chromate.—A concentrated solution of the dicyanobisethylenediamine cobaltic sulphate was treated with an excess of potassium chromate solution. The mixture was heated on the water-bath, filtered and cooled. Beautiful yellow needle-shaped crystals separated on standing. These were washed and dried as usual. {Found : Co, 17.66 ; Cr, 7.72 ; H₂O (by loss at 105°), 13.06. [Co(CN)₂(en)₂]₂ CrO₄·5H₂O requires Co, 17.66 ; Cr, 7.79 H₂O, 13.47 per cent}.

Dicyanobisethylenediamine-cobaltic Molybdate.—A concentrated solution of dicyanobisethylenediamine cobaltic sulphate was treated with an excess of sodium molybdate solution. The mixture was concentrated on the water-bath and filtered to remove the suspended matters. The filtrate on standing for a few days, deposited fine needle-shaped yellow crystals. These were washed and dried as usual. {Found : Co, 16.97 ; Mo, 13.75 ; H₂O (by loss at 105°), 10.28. [Co(CN)₂(en)₂]₂ MoO₄·4H₂O requires, Co, 17.00 ; Mo, 13.83 ; H₂O, 10.37 per cent}.

Dicyanobisethylenediamine-cobaltic-tetrathiocyanatodiammino chromiate was prepared by mixing equimolecular solutions of dicyanobisethylenediamine-cobaltic salt and ammonium tetrathiocyanato-diammino chromiate. The substance forms very sparingly soluble rose-coloured silky crystals. These were washed and dried as usual. {Found : Co, 10.34 ; Cr, 9.23 ; N, 29.09 ; H₂O (by loss at 105°), 3.11. [Co(CN)₂(en)₂] [Cr(SCN)₄(NH₃)₂].H₂O requires Co, 10.41 ; Cr, 9.17 ; N, 29.63 ; H₂O, 3.18 per cent}.

Dicyanobisethylenediamine-cobaltic mercurichloride was obtained as heavy yellow needle-shaped crystals when a concentrated solution of dicyanobisethylenediamine cobaltic chloride was treated with a saturated solution of mercuric chloride. The product was washed and dried as before. {Found : Co, 11.05 ; Cl, 19.64 ; Hg, 37.43. [Co(CN)₂(en)₂] Cl.HgCl₂ requires Co, 10.97 ; Cl, 19.58 ; Hg, 37.29 per cent}.

Dicyanobisethylenediamine-cobaltic cuprichloride was prepared by mixing a concentrated solution of dicyanobisethylenediamine cobaltic chloride with an excess of cupric chloride. The mixture was heated and filtered to separate the insoluble matters. The solution was then concentrated to a small volume on the water-bath and was kept at the room temperature for a long time, when very fine yellowish green crystals separated from the solution. The product was washed and dried as usual. {Found : Co, 8.29 ; Cl, 24.71 ; Cu, 17.78 ; H₂O (by loss at 105°), 25.0. [Co(CN)₂(en)₂] Cl.2CuCl₂·10H₂O requires Co, 8.25 ; Cl, 24.79 ; Cu, 17.76 ; H₂O, 25.17 per cent}.

Dicyanobisethylenediamine-cobaltic mercuribromide was obtained by concentrating a solution of dicyanobisethylenediamine cobaltic bromide mixed with an excess of mercuric bromide. On cooling, heavy yellow rectangular crystals separated from the solution. These were washed and dried as usual. {Found : Co, 8.45 ; Br, 34.38 ; Hg, 28.72 ; H₂O (by loss at 105°), 3.86. [Co(CN)₂(en)₂] Br.HgBr₂·1.5H₂O requires Co, 8.45 ; Br, 34.35 ; Hg, 28.72 ; H₂O, 3.87 per cent}.

Dicyanobisethylenediamine-cobaltic Cupribromide.—Dicyanobisethylenediamine cobaltic bromide was treated with an excess of copper bromide solution. The yellowish green mixture became violet on concentration on the water-bath. The solution was cooled and allowed to stay for a few days, when dark violet-red crystals separated from the solution. The crystals were washed and dried as before. {Found : Co, 6.0 ; Cu, 13.13 ; Br, 40.95 ; H₂O, 21.97. [Co(CN)₂(en)₂] Br.CuBr₂·12H₂O requires Co, 6.06 ; Cu, 13.05 ; Br, 41.05 ; H₂O, 22.19 per cent}.

Dicyanobisethylenediamine-cobaltic mercuriiodide was prepared by adding pure mercuric iodide to a concentrated solution of dicyanobisethylenediamine cobaltic iodide; the mixture was heated on the water-bath till a portion of mercuric iodide remained undissolved. The mixture was filtered from the excess of mercuric iodide. The filtrate was cooled and left at the room temperature for a few days. A beautiful brownish yellow fine microcrystalline product separated from the solution. This was washed and dried as in the previous cases. {Found: Co, 10.02; I, 43.61; Hg, 17.22. $[\text{Co}(\text{CN})_2(\text{en})_2]_2 \text{HgI}_4$ requires Co, 10.08; I, 43.40; Hg, 17.14 per cent.}

Dicyanobisethylenediamine-cobaltic cuprisulphate crystallised out of a mixture of dicyanobisethylenediamine-cobaltic sulphate and an excess of copper sulphate in concentrated aqueous solution after several days in the form of yellowish green needles in bunches. The crystals were washed and dried as usual. {Found: Co, 11.74; S, 9.50; Cu, 12.37; H_2O (by loss at 105°), 14.37. $[\text{Co}(\text{CN})_2(\text{en})_2]_2 \text{SO}_4 \cdot 2\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Co, 11.55; S, 9.40; Cu, 12.45; H_2O , 14.10 per cent.}

The behaviour of the double salt will be described in detail in a subsequent paper dealing with the phase rule study of the system, complex sulphate—copper sulphate—water.

Dicyanobisethylenediamine-cobaltic cobaltosulphate.—The concentrated solution of the dicyanobisethylenediamine cobaltic sulphate was treated with an excess of cobalt sulphate solution. The mixture was heated on the water-bath and filtered. The filtrate was left in air for crystallisation for a few days, when a brown coloured silky microcrystalline substance separated out of the solution. The product was washed and dried as usual. {Found: Co, 22.59; S, 9.22; H_2O (by loss at 105°), 17.0. $[\text{Co}(\text{CN})_2(\text{en})_2]_2 \text{SO}_4 \cdot 2\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 10\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Co, 22.52; S, 9.16; H_2O , 17.28 per cent.}

Dicyanobisethylenediamine-cobaltic nickelosulphate was obtained as a pea-green crystalline product from dicyanobisethylenediamine cobaltic sulphate and nickel sulphate as described in the case of the previous compounds. {Found: Co, 10.85; Ni, 10.69; S, 8.82; H_2O (by loss at 105°), 20.04. $[\text{Co}(\text{CN})_2(\text{en})_2]_2 \text{SO}_4 \cdot 2\text{NiSO}_4 \cdot 12\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Co, 10.90; Ni, 10.72; S, 8.87; H_2O , 19.95 per cent.}

Dicyanobisethylenediamine-cobaltic argentithiosulphate.—When silver nitrate solution in the cold was added to that of an excess of dicyanobisethylenediamine cobaltic thiosulphate, the dirty yellow precipitate, formed at first, went into solution with the formation of argentithiosulphate of the complex. Addition of silver nitrate solution was stopped just before a permanent precipitate appeared. This was filtered and the filtrate was kept in a cold place for a few days. A yellow, sparingly soluble solid separated out of the solution. This was washed and dried as usual. It gradually darkens on keeping for several days. {Found: Co, 15.03; Ag, 18.30; S, 13.42. $3[\text{Co}(\text{CN})_2(\text{en})_2]_2 \text{S}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 2 \text{Ag}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$ requires Co, 14.89; Ag, 18.15; S, 13.46 per cent.}

Dicyanobisethylenediamine-cobaltic cuprothiosulphate was prepared like the previous compound by adding a solution of copper sulphate to an ice-cold concentrated solution of dicyanobisethylenediamine cobaltic thiosulphate. The yellow precipitate, first formed, dissolved with the formation of the complex cuprothiosulphate. After a few days, a yellow, sparingly soluble crystalline product separated from the solution. {Found: Co, 12.50; Cu, 20.43; S, 17.23. $2[\text{Co}(\text{CN})_2(\text{en})_2]_2 \text{S}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 3\text{Cu}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$ requires Co, 12.66; Cu, 20.46; S, 17.16 per cent.}